

PECULARITIES OF TRANSLATING SOME SPECIFIC RELATIONS IN THE TEXT

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Abstract

The article deals with some ways of translating a text. Because of functionalism the author differentiates meaningful elements and structural points of the texts, emphasizes dominant logical-semantic relations between components of the scientific text aimed at resultative approach in a process of translating texts and perceiving them by the addressee.

The author describes translating some specific elements of the text: semantic components.

Functioning of some elements in the structure of the text, ways of representing them with the aim of keeping the idea of the creator in a process of translating are analyzed in this article.

The segments of the authentic scientific texts are used for analysis.

Using semantic interpretation the author of this article depicts specific features of the texts (in particular, non-traditional functions of lexemes, implicitly of presenting fragments of the text, etc.).

All that would give the opportunity to make a translated text adequate.

Keywords: a text, cognition, logical-semantic relations, semantic components, lexeme, semes, implicity.

Introduction

The text as a product of human lingvocognitive studying represented by studying its phenomenological structure.

The cognitive aspect in translation was set out in research works of Z.K. Akhmetzhanova, M.Sh.Musatayeva, Zh.Kh. Salchanova, I.D.Frishberg, M. Zwillig, etc.

In most works on cognitive linguistics in the direction of translation the assessment of the theoretical positions of the authors is based on the specifics of literary translation. Also some cognitive linguistic research is presented in the field of scientific and technical language (in particular, technical terminology).

By promoting the text to the position of the object of translation, we found that the unit of translation should be such an element that would incorporate not only linguistic parameters, but also the parameter of cognition. That's why we propose to introduce the term "segment of cognition" as a working term for a unit of textual material (both: written and oral; in this case, the text acts as the highest communicative unit; it is understood as something already reproduced) in a process of translation.

Materials and methods

As materials for the study were used authentic texts of the philological sphere. The leading methods to study this problem are the method of analysis and synthesis, the method of continuous sampling.

Results and discussion

Recent decades have documented a considerable amount of solid researches devoted to the description of translation and its process, a role of translation, etc.

Some years earlier, it was proposed to take a unit of thought as a unit of translation (A. Malblanc, as well as J.-P. Vinet and J. Darbelne), the smallest segment of the text (O.Kade).

We agree totally with the remark made by R. Jakobson (R. Jakobson, 1985), that any of the modern languages is able to express, describe any fragment of reality.

We also accept the conclusion of N.K.Garbovsky that languages divide reality in different ways, describe the same phenomena and objects differently, paying attention to their signs [1].

At the same time, the lingvo-cognitive essence of the translation process is insufficiently highlighted.

The scientific paradigm, which takes into account both the smallest segment and the largest segment of the text as an object of translation, allows us to consider the translation process as the creation of a complete speech-conscious whole.

With this approach, primary attention is paid to the semantic side of the statement. The first one is mainly focused on the analysis of the linguistic form, the second – on the complex analysis of translation reaching one or another level of the functional conditionality. These paradigms have given a rise to a number of different theories of translation. One of the most important, in our opinion, is lingvo-cognitive.

It is known in linguistics that each text has a language system beyond it; linguistic regularities undoubtedly operate in the text and constitute the most important aspect of its organization. The language dictates not only the rules for constructing phrases and sentences, but also the rules for generating texts.

A text, as it is discovered, as a new grade of functioning of language units has its own specific features. One of them, in our opinion, is relations between segments of the whole.

In our previous investigations (Ramazanova, 2013) we distinguished logical-semantic relations (with its semes) between parts of the text (particularly, art and scientific texts).

Logical-semantic relations, according to our definition, are relations established on the basis of relations

between events and processes (represented by the subject, object, predicate and expressed by the author of speech) occurring in real reality and relations characterizing the perception of the addressee) [2].

It must be mentioned, that in our previous investigations the term 'the supra-phrasal unity' was described and qualified as a unit of the text. But as for the text for translation the other term is represented: 'the segment of cognition'.

This conception reveals the content of that segment of the text which is complete in a logical way and perceived by the recipient (i.e. by a translator) further for addressee.

The segment of cognition (future use – the CS) is a unit in which an intention of the authentic text is revealed; so, a translated part is perceived making an impression on the addressee. In the structure of any segment of cognition can be logical-semantic relations between its parts.

Logical-semantic relations are relations established on the basis of relations between events and processes (represented by the subject, object, predicate and expressed by the author of speech) occurring in reality and relations characterizing the perception of the addressee (Ramazanova, 2013).

Huge importance has knowledge of the fact that each of them has its semes. Among them a great research interest get the non-traditional functions of semes, lexemes, the non-traditional functions of some conjunctions and adverbs in the structure of the text, a polysemy of some functional words, the non-traditional functions of lexemes, ways of representing semes.

As you know, each style represents a person in a different way and uses grammatical forms and constructions in its own way giving preference to one or another of them. So, in a scientific text the subject of the action is deliberately kept away, since it is aimed to express the indefinitely personal meaning of the action and focus on the action (event) which is important in itself.

Anyway, the author of the speech uses all sorts of techniques to convey information, in turn, in the process of translation the subject of speech is obliged to convey the intention of the author.

In this regard, in the process of translation it is paramount to take into account the non-traditional functions of lexemes and semes of the text.

This problem with the linguistic status (in particular the polysemantic nature of some functional words within the framework of the text) was highlighted by us in our previous scientific work (Ramazanova, 2007).

So, we present illustrations to the aforesaid.

Example 1:

When a propagandist uses *argumentum ad hominem*, he wants to distract our attention from the issue under consideration with personal attacks on the people involved him. For example, when Lincoln issued the Emancipation Proclamation, some people responded by calling the "baboon." But Lincoln's long arms and awkward carriage had nothing to do with the merits of the Proclamation or the question of whether or not slavery should be abolished.

The above example contains the lexeme "but" in its structure with its unconventional function. In particular the lexeme "but" does not oppose parts (traditional function is to display opposition being a lexeme of the seme "opposition of the contrastive type of logical-semantic relations) of the CS, but rather unites them in a semantic sense. In other words it takes a function of the lexeme of the seme "actual connection" of the the connective type of logical-semantic relations.

Example 2:

If complex language and its use seems specific to the human species and nearly universal, the early psycholinguists reasoned that it must be biologically based. In other words, humans possess a specific, innate capacity for language. But even though language use is nearly universal, it doesn't follow that underlying language rules are also universal.

The limitless of its possibilities put it to the position in which it becomes a sema "correction" of the explanatory type. This token introduces the part that corrects the previous one and thus gives an explanation of its content.

An unconventional way of introducing the seme "supplementation" reveals itself in the use of the word "but" as a lexeme of this seme.

Example 3:

And if he is concerned about the question why an oculist is an eye-doctor is a meaning postulate, while Washington is the capital of the United States is not, he can be assured that there is a rigorous procedure for making this distinction, namely, to list the former sentence under the heading "meaning postulates" and not to list the latter. But it is clear that such an ad-hoc approach to the problem of classification and characterization of elements in particular language will be of no help to linguistics, who are interested in the GENERAL GROUNDS by which these elements and relations are established in each particular case.

In the example above additional information is detected.

Besides, the lexeme "but" can act as a connector of the seme "purpose" of the causative type.

Let's see. Example 4:

There are several senses in which a physicist can be said to be dealing with idealized situations. On the other hand, he deals with simple objects in the laboratory, such as balls rolling down an inclined plane, rather than with avalanches storming down a mountainside: he will attempt to explain the latter as a complex case of the laws established in terms of the behavior of the simple objects. But he does this on the basis of the assumption, which he will attempt in every way to verify, that complex objects follow the same laws outside the laboratory as simple objects within it: all these objects are part of the same universe, and are composed of matter with the same fundamental properties.

So, in a process of translation the translator should translate such frames of the text into frames in which the principle of antithesis is realized and oppositely restrictive and oppositely conceding meanings are expressed.

The lexeme "and" also has a non-traditional function, i.e. it can be a lexeme of the other semes.

Example:

An analogy is a comparison between two ideas, events or things. But comparisons can be fairly made only when the things compared are alike in significant ways. When they are not, false analogy is the result. A famous example of this is the proverb ‘Don’t change horses the middle of a stream’, often used as an analogy to convince voters to change administrations in the middle of a war or other crisis. But the analogy is misleading because there are so many differences between things compared. In what ways is a war or political crisis like a stream? the President on head of state really very much like a horse? And is a nation of millions of people comparable to a man trying to get across a stream.

(Logical Syntax and Semantics)

In the structure of this CS the lexeme “and” has a function of the lexeme of the seme “comparison”: the roles of millions of people were compared with respect to the role of the president. As a rule, this union is a lexeme of the seme “connection” of the the connective type of logical-semantic relations between the frames of the text.

As our researched material presents the adverb “again” also may have the function of the lexemes of another seme.

Example:

One of the most famous examples of the two-extremes fallacy in recent history is the slogan, “America: Love it or leave it”, with its implicit suggestion that we either accept everything just as it is in America today without complaint – or get out. Again, it should be obvious that there is a whole range of action or belief between those two extremes.

(Logical Syntax and Semantics)

In the structure of this CS the lexeme “and” is in a function of the lexeme of the seme “addition”.

The next example highlights a non-traditional function of the lexeme “so”, as a rule it is a lexeme of the seme “generalization”.

Example:

They begged the Romans to return, but a single legion of Romans soldiers – all that could be spared – helped very little. So the Celts sent a call to “parts across the seat” (as the Venerable Bede, the ancient historian, put it), asking various Germanic leaders in northern Europe to come to them.

(This text and you)

The lexeme “so” is explicated as a lexeme of the seme “cause”: it doesn’t generalize, but illustrates and gives reasons of the further actions of the Celts because of the very little help.

As it is mentioned in our earlier researches the lexemes “first”, “second”, etc. dissect the informative space of the statement according to the degree of significance. There is a downward gradation of values: from greater importance to less.

Very interesting and unusual way of the seme “development” of the enumerative type of logical-semantic relations is observed in our linguistic material. This allows considering that an enumeration is not always presented by ordinal numbers. Let’s illustrate this point.

Example:

The remainder of the chapter is devoted to an explanation of these terms (I). First, we discuss this text in general (II). Then we distinguish three often confused terms: speech, language and communication, and look at some special qualities of language itself (III).

(This text and you)

In this SC the allied word “then” acts as a non-traditional lexeme showing the enumeration of actions removes the tension in the graduation scale.

Except knowledge of the non-traditional ways of compiling sentences in one frame with the help of lexemes, that depict some logical-semantic relations, a translator must take into account implicit way of expressing these relations.

Example:

Most historians say that these Germanic people were of three major tribes, plus a scattering of others (1). They were Jutes, Saxons, and Angles, arriving in that order probably (2).

In this frame the seme “refinement” of the explanatory type of logical-semantic relations is expressed implicitly. The second part of the S. of C. clarifies the first one detailing it in the listings of common nouns.

The seme “supplementation” of the connective type of logical-semantic relations can be introduced implicitly and moreover can be enclosed in brackets. In such cases the addresser has the intention to give additional information not interrupting the main idea of his view.

Example:

What is the source of this ‘greater adequacy’ of the suggested approach? It lies in the fact that this approach adds certain primitive notions to the customary ones of linguistic theory. (The primitive notions of a theory are those that are not analyzed within the theory, but are taken for granted as a basis for constructing the theory.) But what in fact are these primitive notions?

(Logical Syntax and Semantics)

So the part in brackets is additional information: i.e. the seme “supplementation” is presented.

Schematic ways of presenting the seme “illustration” of the explanatory type of logical-semantic relations are allowed within the frame of the scientific text.

Example:

Constituents can be added or deleted to form a variety of noun phrase types. For example, under this phrase-structure rule, we can form *the big hat, those red apples, his car, the baby, my yellow shirt*, and so on.

Likewise, verb phrases can be subjected to the same element or constituent analysis. For example,

VP→VI

VP→VT + NP

Psycholinguistic Theory:

A Syntactic Model

The transformation of one CS into another on the basis of parallel sentences with the same type of relationship is also worth describing. This is confirmed with the language material.

In the illustrative sample below, the functional-narrative compositional-speech form has been transformed into a reflexive-cognitive one. At the beginning

of the extract there was information about what the subject of speech came to know (he is also the author of speech): about his personal view on the development of the language and about what their language actually represents; then the subject of speech began to reason about the commission of a crime against himself by those who don't recognize the purpose of the language.

Example:

I have been told that my view is cranky and pedantic, that I want to keep the language from growing, and to impose a standard and rigid. Far from it our language should be specific and concrete, eloquent possible, playful where possible and personal so that we don't all sound alike. Instead, high crimes and misdemeanors are visited and those who commit them do not understand that the crimes are against themselves. The language belongs to all of us. We have no more valuable possession.

In linguistics such an opinion was expressed that there are three main relations between the parts of the whole: connective, contrastive and causative: This is because....., This means that....., Take, for example... - these are the so-called "service sentences", for which the function of linking independent sentences is the main one. And this kind of connection is mainly characteristic of scientific prose.

We expand this list of types with adding a fourth element: explanatory. This conclusion is based on the research practical material as well as on the theoretical one.

Conclusions

Lingvo-cognitive approach in studying phenomenological structure of the text as a product illuminates the cognitive aspect. This aspect should be transmitted in a process of translation.

The analysis of the authentic linguistic material of texts allowed revealing the scientific text as an intellectual product that requires correctness and accuracy of compiling or reading. The aim can be achieved by knowledge and skills to use of the above given information.

The polysemantic nature of some functional words within the framework of the text, an implicit way of expressing some logical-semantic relations between the segments of the text may cause problems for translator if he does not take into consideration the semantic aspect of parts of the text

The given provides the correctness and accuracy of translation. This supposes its adequate translation.

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